

Linguistics Impact on Classic and Modern Tamil Films

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Human beings share the same common problems, a film can only be understood if it depicts these properly.

- Akira Kurosawa

Films or movies all have been watching them since the advent of cinema and television in our lives. Earlier there was just a national channel which would show movies on weekends, saving the efforts of human going to the hall. Then the cable television was emerged, but nowadays the internet made the scope of watching films at one's own convenience.

India is the prodigious producer of films in the world but no one actually pay much attention to evaluate the effect of movies on youth and the impact of film in society. The present paper focusses what is the role of the movies in our lives and we need to weigh the pros and cons of the movies with its language.

Films are considered as the social activators and language is the expression of community. Many of the customs and traditions of different parts of world are shown in films. Language starts with ear, when a baby starts to talk, he or she does it by hearing the sounds and imitating the words. The gift of imitation gives gift of speech. But it depends mainly on the brought up surroundings of a particular language. On the same way everyone imitate what they ever saw in films in their mundane life. Therefore in our common life films are considered as the major tool to convey everything, whether it is psychological or sociological problems. But the messages were conveyed straightforward to common people with the help of language. In classical cinemas some legends used the language to convey their political views. M.Karunanidhi, Sivaji Ganesan, M.G. Ramachandiran, CHO.S.Ramasamy seems to be the legends of classical Tamil who were the pioneers in using language as a tool to elevate their policies.

Tamil Nadu's first Chief Minister, C.N. Annadurai along with M. Karunanidhi, were the first scriptwriters, who pushed forth the agenda of Dravidian Ideologies. Their biggest hit was the film Parasakthi released in the year 1952, which carried reformist views on the social

hierarchy set by the caste system and glorified movement. The film was also the debut of two other DMK founders, Sivaji Ganesan and S.S. Rajendiran, both of whom went on to become legends of Tamil cinema. The meaningful and hard hitting dialogues written by M. Karunanidhi and that awe inspiring dialogues were delivered by Sivaji Ganesan in the court scene. More importantly it scoffed at judicial system that was blind to the pain and suffering of the common man. It discussed the theme of religion, judiciary and society.

M.G. Ramachandiran popularly called as M.G.R. began his film career in 1936 on the film of Sati Leelavati. Later M.G.R. was strongly associated with the Dravidian Progress Federation. The party grew out of movement against the brutal social order of the era in which lower caste Tamils were denied public resources and often forbidden even to wear shoes or ride bicycles. The D.M.K. packaged its propaganda in the form of popular actions entertainments, using catchy songs to instil Tamil pride, comedy to mock its enemies and extravagant oratory to attract the audience. In 1972 M.G.R. founded the A.I.A.D.M.K. and took most of the movie magic with him. The rabble-rousing songs he had lip-synced in his films, "How long will they fool us / in this land of ours?"-became his party anthem. His fans clubs doubled as party chapters, in a readymade organization that in 1977 was instrumental in winning him the Chief Minister's seat. The main reason of his victory persuaded by using the film with refined language to easily attracted the common people. In his movies M.G.Ramachandiran performed unique, exciting, creative catchy lines with enthusiastic tone. It made even uneducated people to get easily attracted with his ideologies. The pronunciation of language was refined and there were no need of unwanted dialogues or awkward speeches.

CHO. S. Ramasamy made his debut in 1963 with the movie PaarMagalePaaras comedian, but his dialogue deliverance and political criticism made the people to know their common life situation. His political criticism made several impact in common people. Once a group of people threw rotten egg at him for his political criticism, but he never showed angry and surprised everyone with his intellectual words of "Ayya, why throw raw eggs at me, when you can make me an omelette?" The entire crowd burst into laughter. His speech and criticism about hierarchical system of politics gave the enigma for common people. He never used clumsy words or hard words to expose his thoughts. He used language disciplined and well determinedly.

Movies are the reflections of society both present and past. Movie show aftermath of a war, social evils, political strategies and human rights. They create awareness, build civic sense, and ensure public morality. In classic movies, the pronunciation of the language was clear without grammatical error. Because films are the platter of various disciplines and it shows history, culture, science, politics more. So, the language must be a civilized one. But nowadays in modern films they used clumsy and arrogant words for their advertisements. It was easily acquired by all people and used in their day today life. Most of the classic movies depends upon the protagonist and his good characters, which induced the people to carry the good habits and motivates them to achieve something. Every human has the capability to acquire what they see or hear. Because visual medium is considered as the means of better education. In classical period, people loved and crushed with cinematic character and their speaking styles. After M.G.R's political victory many of the people tattoos his name in their hands with an admiration admires for his ideologies. It contrast to the modern, that here gave the major importance for antagonist and his arrogant characters. In the modern tendency, people try to follow the antagonist character with an admiration of fictional characters which made them to lose their humanity. But the actors used the language only for the advertisement of films. It was mistakenly understood by the students and youngsters, they felt the use of clumsy language made themselves to be higher one.

Additionally, lyrics of the songs also differed from classic and modern. In the classic evergreen songs had plenty of themes in itself. It was not only for entertainment but also made people to

learn the self-motivation, social awareness and the patriotic feelings. The language of the song and the using of the words were literally perfect. Even the songs were genuinely pronounced with emphasis on language's grammatical sense. They give importance to concept of the song with little bit of music. Presently, most of the songs are famous only by its music, rather there are no more concepts with its clear language.

Media is the powerful tool to convey the messages. Every work of art try to made impact on the audience. Some of the works will be understand by the audience only they had skills of reading and educated. But movies doesn't depend whether they were educated or uneducated. The main purpose of the films, that made the uncivilized people and uneducated peoples also easily understand the concept of films. The important elements in using the language in movies is to make uncivilized a civilized one. In the classic movies, the usage of language made the cinema actor to push himself as the Chief Minister. M.G.Ramachandiran perfectly used the language to attract the people with his ideologies, whether they were educated or uneducated made them to change even uncivilized to civilized with the help of classical movies.

As the vice versa on the modern movies that it made the impacts in wrong way. Nowadays school students also used unwanted and abusive words with the effect of modern movies. This paper gives importance to the choice of words in the movies and the popularized figure who have the most of followers should be conscious in using the words. William Shakespeare gives the thoughts about words, "My words fly up, my thoughts remain below. Words without thoughts never to heaven go".

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